

Expression of CD83 in tissue-resident regulatory T cells maintains local homeostasis and restricts effector cells in allergic asthma

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Abstract

Non-lymphoid tissue Tregs (NLT-Tregs) are critical for tissue homeostasis, inflammation control, and induction of mucosal repair. Recent single-cell RNA sequencing data identified expression of CD83 as part of a NLT-Treg signature, however its biological significance for this specialized Tregs was not yet fully understood. In our previous investigations, we found that conditional deletion of CD83 (CD83cKO) disrupts stability and differentiation of lymphoid Tregs and exacerbates autoimmune responses. The present study explores for the first time the role of CD83 expression by lung-resident Tregs to understand its importance in barrier tissues. We report that CD83-deficient lung Tregs are less differentiated but more activated, resulting in unrestrained T cell activation. Furthermore, using an allergic asthma model, CD83cKO mice showed an accelerated disease progression, with augmented eosinophilic inflammation, driven by Th2-biased T cell responses. CD83cKO Tregs exhibited an enhanced responsiveness to IL-4, leading to insufficient control of Th2-differentiation from naïve T cells. These findings underscore the pivotal role of CD83 in the NLT-Treg-mediated modulation of inflammation, especially in the context of Th2 responses. Overall, our results highlight CD83 as a key player in maintaining tissue homeostasis and modulating inflammatory responses, suggesting potential therapeutic implications for inflammatory disorders such as asthma.

Introduction

Regulatory T cells (Tregs) are vital components of our immune system, serving to suppress proinflammatory immune responses, prevent autoimmune processes, and facilitate tissue homeostasis and regeneration following injury. Tregs can be further subdivided into two subsets of different ontogeny: thymic or natural Tregs (nTregs), which are generated during thymocyte differentiation, and inducible, peripheral Tregs (pTregs), which are generated in the periphery from CD4⁺ naïve T cells upon interaction with environmental antigens presented by mucosal tissue-resident dendritic cells in the presence of interleukin-2 (IL-2) and transforming growth factor (TGFβ) [1]. By contrast, nTregs undergo several reprogramming steps during their development in the thymus before migrating into secondary lymphoid tissues (LTs), such as the spleen and the lymph nodes (LNs) as well as non-lymphoid tissues (NLTs), like visceral adipose tissue, skin, colon or the lungs [2]. NLT Tregs play a significant role in maintaining tissue homeostasis, limiting inflammation and allergic immune responses, thereby facilitating the induction of mucosal repair mechanisms. Notably, these NLT Tregs upregulate specific surface receptors, e.g., ST2 and KLRG1 and transcription factors such as GATA3 to fulfill their roles within their specific environments. While KLRG1 plays an essential role in the late differentiation of Tregs and their ability to exert suppressive functions at sites of inflammation [3, 4], ST2⁺ Tregs, following recruitment by the alarmin IL-33, initiate specific pathways to regulate inflammation in different non-lymphoid tissues [2, 5–8]. Furthermore, ST2⁺ Tregs are highly activated, strongly suppressive and show a Th2-biased phenotype by expressing GATA3 and producing Th2 cytokines [3, 7, 9]. Due to the specialized functions of different NLT-Tregs, which are imprinted by the respective tissue, identification of markers that uniformly distinguish these cells from their lymphoid counterparts is crucial for understanding their biology and

function. Recently, scRNA-Seq analyses of NLT-Tregs derived from skin and colon revealed an increased expression of the CD83 molecule when compared to Tregs from spleens and lymph nodes [10]. We have already demonstrated that a Treg-specific deletion of CD83 (CD83cKO) results in impaired stability and differentiation of Tregs, leading to exacerbated autoimmune responses and disturbed resolution of inflammation [11]. Interestingly, these CD83cKO Tregs display reduced ST2 and KLRG1 expression already in lymphoid organs, and even more so in the lamina propria of the colon. The less differentiated state as well as impaired gut homing of CD83cKO Tregs into this specific NLT accounts for an exacerbated disease course in an adoptive transfer colitis model. Given the altered phenotype of CD83cKO cells with regard to NLT Treg markers, we hypothesize a crucial role of CD83 expression in Tregs involved in the homeostasis of tissues, especially of those in close contact with the environment, exerting barrier functions. To analyze this further, we investigated the phenotype of CD83cKO mice with special focus on the lungs. Our analysis revealed that lung-resident Tregs not only showed impaired late differentiation in CD83cKO mice, but were also highly activated and less able to prevent overshooting cytokine responses upon stimulation. In an inflammatory lung specific model for asthmatic disease, we observed an increased Th2 inflammation, excessive eosinophilia, and aggravated airway hyperresponsiveness (AHR). Mechanistically, CD83cKO Tregs displayed an increased response to IL-4, which directly led to an enhanced Th2 differentiation and proliferation. Collectively, we reveal that CD83 deletion in Tregs disrupts tissue homeostasis and leads to elevated pathogenic Th2 immune responses.

Results

Lung resident CD83cKO Tregs show a higher activation status and fail to suppress T cell activation. In our previous study, we observed a reduction of FoxP3⁺ Tregs in LTs as well as the lamina propria of CD83cKO mice [11]. Thus, we first analyzed the frequency of splenic and lymph node derived LT-Tregs in comparison with Tregs isolated from the lungs. As expected, LT-Treg frequencies were significantly reduced in CD83cKO, and a similar trend was observed in the lungs (Fig. 1a). Regarding NLT-Treg markers, such as ST2 and KLRG1 in these organs, we observed a trend towards reduced ST2 surface level expressions in Tregs from the lungs, whereas the frequency of KLRG1⁺ CD83cKO Tregs was drastically decreased (Fig. 1b, c). In contrast, Treg-specific receptors, such as ICOS and CD25 exhibited no changes upon CD83 deletion (Supplementary Fig. 2a, b). However, GITR, a receptor associated with a higher activation status of T cells, was strongly upregulated in all tissues (Fig. 1d). This is in line with our previous results, where CD83cKO Tregs exhibit an activated, proinflammatory phenotype.

Due to the significant decrease in KLRG1⁺ Treg, with a concomitant elevated expression of GITR in CD83cKO mice, we examined the capacity of NLT-Tregs to suppress T cell activation and cytokine secretion. To this end, we stimulated cells from either the lungs or cervical lymph nodes (cLNs) with anti-CD3/anti-CD28 and assessed the cytokine levels. Interestingly, we observed a generally elevated cytokine release of Th1, Th2, Th9, Th17 and Th22-specific cytokines in lung-derived lymphocytes from CD83cKO mice (Fig. 2a). This was not the case for cLNs, except for increased secretion of IL-17A (Fig. 2a, Supplementary Fig. 3). Furthermore, the chemokine CCL20 was also significantly increased upon T cell

stimulation of CD83cKO lung cells (Fig. 2b). These results suggest that CD83 deletion in Tregs results in the failure to prevent activation of tissue-resident T cells, leading to escalating cytokine production and chemotactic signals. We reasoned that this phenotype might directly translate into a promotion of inflammatory processes in the lung tissue. Thus, we examined the *in vivo* relevance of our findings in a lung specific inflammation model of allergic asthma.

CD83cKO mice develop exacerbated airway hyperresponsiveness (AHR) and enhanced eosinophilic inflammation and elevated Th2 immunity. To induce asthmatic disease, mice were immunized twice with ovalbumin (OVA) complexed with alum and subsequently challenged by intranasal application of OVA alone, two weeks after the last immunization (Fig. 3a). Mice that received an intranasal PBS-application served as control group. The lung function of mice was assessed using a non-invasive as well as an invasive method to determine airway hyperresponsiveness (AHR), to increasing doses of methacholine. OVA-treated CD83cKO mice exhibited signs of impaired lung function in both assessments (Fig. 3c, Supplementary Fig. 4a-b). We observed an increased enhanced pause (Penh) in OVA-treated CD83cKO mice during the 12.5mg/ml methacholine (Mch) challenge, indicating airway narrowing (Fig. 3b). Furthermore, OVA-treated CD83cKO mice displayed a significant impaired lung functionality, as evidenced by strongly increased resistance (Fig. 3c) and elastance, as well as a significant decrease in compliance of the lung (Supplementary Fig. 4a-b). As these results suggested altered lung tissue functionality, we next assessed the lung tissues from asthma mice by histology. We selected small bronchioles characterized by a comparatively lesser thickness in both connective and smooth muscle tissues, as well as the extracellular matrix, in contrast to the more substantial dimensions observed in larger airways. An increased collagen deposition around the bronchioles in CD83cKO was observed, which was already evident in PBS-challenged mice and got even more prominent upon asthma induction (Fig. 3d). Semi-quantitative evaluation of these histological measurements revealed significantly increased collagen thickness in the lung tissue of CD83cKO mice, indicating pathogenic morphological changes (Fig. 3e). Supplementary data include complete histological images (see Supplementary Fig. 5), confirming the absence of serositis or plaque formation in PBS mice and highlighting the OVA-dependent morphological changes not exclusively focally, but also in other regions of the lung. Additionally, we revealed enhanced thickness of the smooth muscle tissue surrounding the bronchioles in untreated CD83cKO mice, with a more pronounced effect in OVA-treated versus PBS-treated mice. Furthermore, OVA-treated CD83cKO mice exhibited elevated peribronchial and perivascular infiltration of eosinophils and lymphocytes (Supplementary Fig. 6).

One hallmark of OVA-induced asthma is the infiltration of inflammatory eosinophils [12]. Therefore, we isolated single cells from the lungs as well as the bronchioalveolar lavage fluids (BALFs) of asthmatic mice and assessed the cellular composition. Strikingly, we observed a massive infiltration of eosinophils into the lungs of OVA-treated CD83cKO mice, which was even more pronounced in the BALFs, where eosinophils made up almost 80% of all infiltrating immune cells (Fig. 4a-c). Moreover, the frequency of the inflammatory Siglec^F^{high} eosinophil subset was significantly higher in lungs of CD83cKO mice. Importantly, this change in immune cell composition was not observed in respective cLNs, highlighting

the lung-specific effects of CD83-deletion (Supplementary Fig. 8a-b). These results demonstrate that CD83-deficient Tregs exacerbate the progression of asthma and enhance eosinophilic inflammation.

Exacerbated asthmatic disease in CD83cKO mice is driven by insufficient control of Th2 immunity. In addition to eosinophils, we also examined the CD4⁺ T cell population in different tissues. Interestingly, CD83cKO mice did not exhibit any differences in CD4⁺ T cell frequencies when compared to the control (Ctrl) mice (Supplementary Fig. 9a, Fig. 5a). Furthermore, we assessed the expression of different surface receptors on both CD4⁺ and CD25⁺Foxp3⁺ Treg cells in the lung. Notably, CD83cKO mice displayed significantly increased GITR expression levels even before OVA treatment, and this expression was further enhanced following treatment (Fig. 5b-c, Supplementary Fig. 9b-c). The elevated GITR expression has the potential to enhance Th2 cell activity in asthma, contributing to airway inflammation, as has previously been reported [13, 14]. To further pursue the notion of enhanced Th2 responses, we examined effector T cells and observed a significant increase in GATA3⁺Foxp3⁻ T cells in OVA-treated CD83cKO mice (Fig. 5d). When we analysed the expression of additional Th2 markers on effector T cells versus Tregs, we found significantly increased frequencies of ST2⁺/FoxP3⁺ Tregs as well as ST2⁺/FoxP3⁻ effector cells. Remarkably, lung Tregs from CD83cKO mice exhibited a substantial reduction in Foxp3 expression even without challenge. (Fig. 5e-f).

Since ST2 serves as the receptor for IL33, an alarmin released during tissue damage that contributes to tissue homeostasis and the local expansion of NLT-Tregs at the site of inflammation, we assessed circulatory IL33 levels in the serum of asthmatic mice. Our results show a strong tendency towards higher IL33 levels in OVA-treated CD83cKO mice (Supplementary Fig. 10). These data suggest that CD83cKO mice have a higher state of inflammation and are unable to regulate the activity of Th2-specific effector cells in allergic asthma. This notion was further corroborated by cytokine secretion of lung derived immune cells upon ex vivo restimulation with OVA. While cells from PBS-treated mice did not react to OVA restimulation, we observed a strikingly increased release of the Th2-related cytokines IL-5 and IL-13 in the cultures of CD83cKO cells from OVA-challenged mice (Fig. 5g). Additionally, there was an increased production of chemokines, such as CCL17, CCL22, and CXCL5, upon restimulation with OVA. Collectively, we reasoned that the dysfunctional state of CD83-deficient Tregs, which is characterized by reduced terminal differentiation and higher expression of GITR, renders these cells unable to confine Th2-responses. Consequently, CD83cKO mice develop an exacerbated disease course which is driven by massive eosinophilia.

CD83-deficient Tregs fail to confine Th2 differentiation and proliferation. To test whether the inability to suppress Th2 responses was specific to the used in vivo model or a Treg-intrinsic defect, we performed Th skewing experiments under Th2 conditions, specifically examining the proliferation and differentiation of CD4⁺ T cells. Therefore, total CD4⁺ T cells were isolated from CD83cKO or control mice, labeled with CellTraceTMViolet and cultivated in the presence of OVA/LPS-pulsed dendritic cells (DCs). As we aimed to dissect the effect of Treg-specific deletion of CD83 on Th2 polarization, we set up our co-cultures using the following conditions: (i) anti-CD3 antibodies were added to initiate a clonal T cell proliferation, (ii)

anti-IFN- γ antibodies added to mitigate Th1 differentiation, and (iii) “full Th2-differentiation” was achieved by the addition of IL-4. In these co-culture experiments, we observed that Treg frequencies remained unaffected (Fig. 6b), although there was a trend towards higher frequencies in cultures with CD83cKO T cells. Notably, while we detected no differences in the expression of Th2 master transcription factor GATA3, when T cells were only activated with anti-CD3, mitigating IFN- γ signaling and thus, Th1 differentiation, already resulted in a significantly higher proportion of GATA3⁺ T cells (Fig. 6c). This effect was drastically enhanced in the presence of IL-4, where we observed an increase of GATA3⁺ T cells, along with a higher replication index in CD83cKO mice, suggesting a more vigorous induction of Th2 differentiation (Fig. 6c-d). When we examined activation markers expressed by CD4⁺ T cells, we found that GITR was significantly increased already under control conditions (anti-CD3 only). This increase became increasingly more pronounced upon addition of anti-IFN- γ and IL-4, paralleling the pattern of GATA3-expression (Fig. 6e). We detected similar behavior for CD25, which was also strikingly increased in CD83cKO cultures under “full” Th2 conditions. In line with the profound Th2 differentiation of CD83cKO-derived T cells, IL-13 cytokine levels were significantly elevated in the supernatants of these cultures (Fig. 6g). Taken together, these data suggest that CD4⁺ T cells from CD83cKO mice are more prone to Th2 differentiation, and this potential is fully unlocked upon stimulation with IL-4.

Sorted CD83cKO Tregs display a higher IL-4 responsiveness with a preserved GITR phenotype. From the above described data, we concluded that IL-4 might have an important function in uncovering the effect of CD83-deletion on Treg biology. IL-4 is known to have context-dependent effects on Tregs: i.e. while IL-4 stabilizes nTregs *in vitro* [15], it can inhibit the differentiation of iTregs from naive CD4⁺ T cells in allergic airway disease [16]. Additionally, it can promote the conversion of Tregs into exFoxp3-Th2 effector cells [17]. Since IL-4 signaling is predominantly mediated via IL-4R α , we first assessed the expression of the respective *Il4ra* transcript in sorted Tregs. Thereby, we detected significantly upregulated *Il4ra* transcripts in CD83cKO Tregs compared to wildtype Tregs (Fig. 7a). To examine the effect of IL-4 stimulation in CD83cKO in more detail, we stimulated sorted Tregs with IL-4 (Fig. 7). As expected from literature reports [15], Foxp3 expression was stabilized and increased upon IL-4 stimulation, but showed no significant differences when comparing CD83cKO cells to controls cells (Fig. 7b). When we analyzed surface receptors on Tregs, the results mirrored those obtained in the coculture experiments, with an increase in CD25 and GITR expression in CD83cKO Tregs following IL-4 stimulation, indicating enhanced activation (Fig. 7c, d). In addition, we examined additional activation markers, including ICOS and CD69 (Fig. 7e, however they were not influenced by the Treg-specific CD83 deletion. To ensure that the observed changes are indeed depending on IL-4 stimulation, we included experiments with IL-4-blocking antibodies before addition of IL-4 which abrogates the observed effects (Supplementary Fig. 12). Taken together, CD83 deletion results in an elevated IL-4-responsiveness leading to a highly activated phenotype.

Altogether, our data disclosed a significant role of CD83 in NLT-Tregs and especially for the suppression of Th2-responses. CD83 deletion in Tregs impairs their regulatory activity towards tissue-resident T cells in the lungs, leading to an increased proinflammatory activated phenotype in the lung and impairing tissue homeostasis. Furthermore, CD83-deficient Tregs are more responsive to IL-4 stimulation, probably

subverting their capacity to suppress Th2 immune responses. This phenotype directly translates into development of aggravated disease symptoms upon induction of Th2-dependent asthma symptoms and provides valuable insights into the key modulatory role of CD83 for Treg biology and function.

Discussion

Most NLT-Tregs, particularly those on barrier sites like the skin, the colon, or the lungs undergo priming in the LTs before migrating to the periphery, displaying specific transcriptomic adaptations. These Tregs undergo final expressional changes, such as including the upregulation KLRG1, ST2, and GATA3 in the NLTs, developing into effector Tregs that surveil the tissue to suppress pathogenic responses at sites of inflammation or injury [2, 10]. Interestingly, recent single-cell sequencing analyses revealed that CD83 is upregulated in these barrier tissue resident Tregs [10]. Our previous findings have already demonstrated that CD83 deletion in Tregs confers an enhanced proinflammatory phenotype and leads to impaired late differentiation with compromised resolution of inflammatory events. More importantly, splenic CD83cKO Tregs already displayed a reduction of ST2 and KLRG1 expression, which implied an even more pronounced impact of CD83-deletion on tissue Tregs. Within the present study, we provide evidence that lung-resident T cells from CD83cKO mice respond to stimulation aCD3/aCD28 with a drastic general increase of cytokine secretion. Since this effect was not observed in cLNs from the same animals, we conclude that it is indeed NLT-specific and propose a crucial role of CD83 in regulating Treg function in barrier tissues. Notably, we observed the most prominent dysregulation of cytokines related to Th17-responses. Additionally, lung lymphocytes of CD83cKO animals secreted increased amounts of CCL20, a chemokine that is important for the recruitment of DCs and Th17 T cells. IL-17 is essential for lung tissue homeostasis and bacterial clearance but excessive release of IL-17 can contribute to fibrosis and pathogenic airway remodeling in the lung including collagen depositions [18]. Intriguingly, we observed morphological changes in the lungs of naïve CD83cKO mice, with epithelial hyperplasticity, hypertrophy of the smooth muscle tissue, and increased collagen deposition surrounding the bronchi even unchallenged mice. These data suggest that deletion of CD83 in Tregs disturbs their capability to maintain tissue integrity even in the absence of inflammation. We also revealed that CD83-deficient Tregs, while exhibiting a phenotype of less terminally differentiated cells, express higher levels of the co-stimulatory molecule GITR. Interestingly, we observed significantly elevated levels of GITR on CD83-deficient Tregs, both in the steady state and in asthma, highlighting the central role of CD83 in Treg biology. GITR is constitutively expressed on nTregs and upregulated on activated CD4⁺ T cells [19]. GITR-mediated signaling is involved in plasticity of Tregs towards a Th9 and Th2 phenotype [13, 20, 21], alters their stability [22], and limits Treg suppressive capacity, leading to the exacerbation of autoimmune diseases and increased resistance to tumors [21, 23]. A recent publication also proved the importance of GITR signaling for the establishment of Th2-driven asthmatic disease [13]. This perfectly aligns with our *in vivo* data in the OVA-induced asthma model, with CD83cKO animals developing more severe disease symptoms, which rely on excessive Th2 responses and concomitant eosinophilia. Moreover, T cells in the lungs of asthmatic CD83cKO mice expressed elevated levels of ST2 and we observed a clear trend towards elevated levels of its ligand IL-33 in the sera of those mice. Stimulation with IL-33 led to

suppressive function of lung-derived Tregs and aggravation of allergen-driven inflammation, which was associated with pathological Th2-like Tregs, secreting IL-5 and IL-13, thereby enhancing airway inflammation [24]. In line with this, we observed that lung lymphocytes from CD83cKO also secreted drastically increased amounts of IL-5 and IL-13 upon restimulation with OVA. While IL-13 is known to induce tissue remodeling, airway hyperresponsiveness and mucus secretion in the lung [25, 26], IL-5 is a key stimulus for recruitment and survival of eosinophils [27]. Concomitantly, we observed increased collagen deposition around the bronchi as well as massive eosinophilia in the lung tissue and the BALF.

In asthma, Th2-type cells are recruited to the site of inflammation in the lung via chemokines such as CCL17 and CCL22 [28, 29], which are both upregulated in asthmatic CD83cKO mice. Lung lymphocytes from asthmatic mice exhibited an increased production of CXCL5 upon restimulation with OVA, which is associated with neutrophil recruitment, but also triggers the specific granule content release of eosinophils [30, 31]. Collectively, these data suggest that CD83-deletion renders Tregs less effective to suppress Th2 responses, leading to an exacerbated asthmatic disease.

When we further analyzed whether CD83-deficient Tregs are able to control Th2 differentiation, we observed that the more the commitment to Th1 differentiation is inhibited, the stronger is the inability of CD83-cKO Tregs to prevent Th2 responses. Experiments using isolated Tregs, disclosed that CD83cKO cells exhibit an elevated expression of IL-4R α , leading to an increased IL-4 responsiveness and increased induction of CD25 and GITR. This is in line with IL-4 hyperresponsiveness leading to STAT6-dependent inhibition of Foxp3 expression, and subsequently, the development of pathogenic Th2 responses [8, 32]. Interestingly, a soluble form of CD83 (sCD83) with well-described immunomodulatory functions [33], has been shown to trigger apoptosis in Th2 cells in a model for allergic rhinitis [34]. Since Tregs up-regulate and stably express CD83 after stimulation [35], and sCD83 can be generated from the membrane-bound form, this adds to the complexity of Treg-mediated control of Th2 responses.

In summary, our findings underscore the crucial role of CD83 regarding the suppressive function of NLT-Tregs and maintenance of tissue homeostasis. Deletion of CD83 in Tregs results in a highly activated and pro-inflammatory phenotype, characterized by elevated expression levels of GITR. In the lungs of CD83cKO mice, we observe impaired late differentiation and a pronounced failure in suppressive function of NLT-Tregs, consequently promoting pathogenic Th2 immunity in an IL-4 dependent manner. Collectively, we provided new evidence that CD83 is a crucial component of Treg-mediated suppression of inflammation, especially of Th2 responses (Fig. 8).

Material and methods

Animals.

All of the mice were maintained on the C57BL/6 strain background. Floxed CD83 animals were generated in our laboratory as described previously [36]. Foxp3-Cre animals were provided by A. Rudensky (University of Washington, Seattle, Washington, USA). For Treg-specific depletion of the CD83 gene, floxed

CD83 animals were crossed with Foxp3-Cre mice (CD83^{fl/fl} Foxp3^{Cre+/-} also called as CD83cKO). The corresponding Cre mice (CD83^{wt/wt} Foxp3^{Cre+/-}) were used as controls (Ctrls) in all experiments. In all experiments, we used an equal distribution of age-matched male and female mice. The mice were housed in a controlled environment with specific pathogen-free conditions, including a temperature of 22°C and humidity between 40% and 50%, following a 12-hour light and 12-hour dark cycle. All animal care and experimental procedures in this study followed the guidelines of the European Community Standards for Laboratory Animal Care and were approved by the local ethics committee. (Administration of Lower Franconia; Reference number 55.2-2532-2-633).

Allergic asthma in vivo mouse model induction

The in vivo ovalbumin-induced allergic asthma mouse model starts with the sensitization process by intraperitoneal (i.p.) injections of 100 µg ovalbumin (OVA; Calbiochem, San Diego, USA) complexed with 10% aluminum potassium sulfate solution (Sigma Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) on days 0 and 7 followed by intranasal challenging with 50 µg OVA, dissolved in PBS, on days 19, 20 and 21. On day 21, whole-body plethysmography using the Buxco system (Data Sciences International (DSI), St. Paul, USA) is performed for non-invasive airway hyperresponsiveness (AHR) measurement. The mice are challenged by increasing doses of methacholine (0, 12.5, 25, and 50 mg/ml) in order to obtain the parameter enhanced pause (Penh). On day 22, invasive AHR provocation test was carried out to analyze the lower respiratory system resistance (Rrs), elastance (Ers) and compliance (Crs) following methacholine challenge (0, 12.5, 25, and 50 mg/ml). The experimental animals were anesthetized (Ketamine, Medetomidine) and underwent tracheotomy to mechanically ventilate them with a blunt cannula via the flexiVent device (SCIREQ Inc., Montreal, Canada). Finally, BAL was performed and mice were sacrificed by cervical dislocation under ongoing anesthesia to isolate heart blood as well as the different tissues for the subsequent assays [37].

Collection of single cell solutions.

a) Spleen

First, the spleen tissue is isolated from the mouse and then ground between the frosted ends of microscope slides. Second, the resulting cell suspension is transferred through a 70 µm cell strainer into a 50 ml tube. Third, the tube is centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 7 minutes at 4°C, and the supernatant is discarded. Fourth, 2 ml of Ammonium-Chloride-Potassium (ACK)-Lysis buffer (0.15 M NH₄Cl, 0.1 mM KHCO₃, 0.1 mM Na₂-EDTA dissolved in ddH₂O) is added for erythrocyte lysis and incubated for 2 minutes at room temperature. Fifth, the lysis is then stopped by filling up the suspension with 1x PBS (Anprotec) up to 35 ml. Sixth, the cells are centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 7 minutes at 4°C, and the supernatant is discarded. Finally, the cells are resuspended in 10 ml of 1xPBS, transferred through another 70 µm cell strainer, and the cell count is determined.

b) Lymph nodes

First, lymph nodes are isolated from the mouse and then ground between the frosted ends of microscope slides. Second, the resulting cell suspension is transferred through a 70 µm cell strainer into a 50 ml tube. Third, the tube is centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 7 minutes at 4°C, and the supernatant is discarded. Finally, the cells are resuspended in 5 ml of 1xPBS and the cell count is determined.

c) Lung

In this procedure, mouse lung was first removed using a scissor and cut into small pieces. For each test, a 2 ml digestion solution was prepared consisting of FCS (5%, Thermo Fischer Scientific), Collagenase-D (1 mg/ml, Roche) and DNase (0,5 mg/ml, Applichem) in SFM-G Medium in C-Tubes. The C-tube was then subjected to the lung program using the gentleMACS Octo Dissociator (Miltenyi Biotec) at 37°C for lung tissue digestion. At the end of the digestion, the contents were passed through a moistened 70 µm Cellstrainer. The threads of the C-tube were rinsed with DMEM-F12, and the tubes were also rinsed. The tube contents were centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 5 minutes at 4°C. Subsequently, erythrocyte lysis was performed by adding 1 ml of ACK-Lysis-Buffer to the pellet for 2 minutes. As next, the pellet was resuspended in 20 ml of 1xPBS to stop the reaction and wash the cells. The cells were then collected by centrifugation and resuspended in 1 ml of PBS/EDTA solution with a concentration of 5 mM. The cell suspension was subsequently subjected to flow cytometry analysis (FACS) and for further characterization and investigation.

Flow cytometry analysis and cell sorting

Single-cell suspensions from different tissues were used for cell surface staining using flow cytometry employed standard procedures and the following conjugated antibodies and reagents: Live/Dead (ThermoFisher Scientific); CD3 (17A2; 1:200), CD4 (RM4-5; 1:200), CD25 (PC61; 1:100), CD45 (30-F11; 1:200), St2 (DIH4; 1:100), KLRG1 (2F1; 1:200), GITR (DTA-1; 1:100), CD11b (M1/70; 1:400), I-A/I-E (M5/114.15.2; 1:200), SiglecF (S17007L; 1:100), Ly6G (1A8; 1:200), (Biolegend). Intracellular staining for Foxp3 (FJK-16s; 1:100) and GATA3 (TWAJ; 1:100) was analyzed using the Foxp3/Transcription Factor Staining Buffer Set from eBioscience. Single-cell suspensions were incubated with appropriate fluorochrome-conjugated monoclonal antibodies and measured on FACSCanto II and FACSFortessa (BD Biosciences) analyzing the data with FlowJo v10 (Tree Star). Sort experiments of CD3 + CD4 + YFP + Tregs were performed on FACS Aria.

Restimulation of cLN and lung derived lymphocytes.

Cells were isolated from the cLNs and from the lung. Cells (1×10^5) were incubated for 48 hours with anti-CD3 (1 µg/ml) and anti-CD28 (1 µg/ml) or for 24 hours with OVA (500 µg/ml) in 100 µl medium consisting of RPMI (Anprotec), 10% fetal bovine albumin (FCS, Merck), 1% penicillin/streptomycin/l-glutamine solution (Sigma) and 0.5 µM β-mercaptoethanol (Roth) (R10 medium) in a 96-well U-bottom plate. Supernatants were collected to determine T helper cytokine and proinflammatory chemokine levels using cytometric bead arrays (BioLegend) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Lung histology

After the lung was removed, a piece was obtained from the left side of the lung and was fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde, which was then embedded in paraffin. Subsequently, the tissue was sectioned using microtome into 5 µm thick serial sections for hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and Sirius-red staining. H&E staining was selected to assess inflammation levels semi-quantitatively. We used Sirius-red staining to quantify morphological changes, such as fibrosis resulting from inflammation in the tissue. Peribronchial collagen was quantified by measuring the collagen thickness (µm) beneath the bronchial epithelium normalized by dividing by the bronchial diameter (µm) [38]. Stainings were analyzed via slide viewer 2.7.0.191696 software (3DHistech, Budapest, Hungary), 20x magnification, scanned by slides scanner P1000 (3DHistech, Budapest, Hungary).

Serum collection

Whole blood was collected from the heart on day 22 of the allergic asthma experiments. After incubation at room temperature (RT) for 30 min, blood was centrifuged (12500 rpm, 5 min, RT) and serum was frozen at -20°C for ELISA analysis.

Bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF)

BALF was collected on day 22 by injecting and aspirating twice 0.8 mL Sterofundin (B. Braun Melsungen AG, Melsungen, Germany) intratracheally in each mouse. Afterwards, BALF was centrifuged at 1500 rpm for 5 min and the supernatants were frozen at -20°C for ELISA analysis. The remaining cell pellet was resuspended in PBS and used for flow cytometric analysis as described below.

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA)

Serum levels of IL33 were determined by using a commercial kit for mouse-IL33 according to the manufacturer's protocol (catalog number: 88-73333, eBioscience).

Generation and stimulation of Bone marrow derived dendritic cells (BMDCs)

The generation of BMDCs followed the methodology previously described by our group [39]. Wildtype DCs were treated with OVA (100 µg/µl, Calbiochem, San Diego, USA) and LPS (10 ng/ml, Sigma Aldrich) for 3 hours long at 37°C, 5% CO₂ and used for co-culture experiments.

DC-T Cell Co-Cultures

To mimic an in vivo situation in a th2-like environment and further analyze the role of CD83 in Tregs, we co-cultured OVA/LPS-treated DCs with CD4+ T cells from Ctrl or CD83cKO mice. CD4+ T cells were isolated using the Mouse CD4+ T cell Isolation Kit, in accordance with the provided protocol (Miltenyi Biotec, Bergisch Gladbach, Germany) from the spleen and mLN followed by CTV (CellTraceViolet, Thermo Fisher Scientific) labeling according to the manufacturer's protocol. Afterward, 1 x 10⁵ CTV-

labeled CD4 + T cells were co-cultured in a 96-well flat bottom plate at a ratio of 20:1 with OVA/LPS-matured DCs (5×10^3). In a final volume of 200 μ l, additionally, three different cytokine mixes were added for 4 days: 1) anti-CD3 only (2,5 ng/ml, 17A2, Biolegend), 2) anti-CD3 and anti-IFN γ (10 μ g/ml, XMG1.2, Biolegend) and 3) anti-CD3/anti-IFN γ and IL-4 (10 ng/ml, Milteny Biotec) (Table 1). Then, cells were harvested, stained with mAbs, and analyzed by flow cytometry. Supernatants and mRNA were isolated as well and stored at -80 for further investigation.

qPCR

The sorted YFP + Tregs as well as the cocultured cells were harvested and lysed with the RLTPlus buffer (Qiagen), and total RNA was isolated by using RNeasy Plus Mini and Micro Kit (Qiagen) according to the manufacturer's protocol. A total of 1 μ g of RNA was used for reverse transcription into cDNA using First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Subsequently, gene expression was determined by using 2x qPCR S'Green BlueMix (Biozym Scientific) on CFX96 Real-Time PCR Detection System (Bio-Rad). All primers were tested for specificity and quality according to the MIQE guidelines (Table 1) [40]. Samples mRNA levels were normalized to the expression of the HPRT reference gene.

Table 1
Primer sequences for qPCR.

Gene	Orientation	sequence
HPRT	forward	5' GTTGGATACAGGCCAGACTTTGTTG 3'
	reverse	5' GATTCAACTTGCGCTCATCTTAGGC 3'
IL-4Ra	forward	5' ACGTGGTACAACCACTTCCA 3'
	reverse	5' CTGGGGTGGGAATCTGGTCC 3'
IL-4 restimulation of YFP + sorted Tregs		

Sorted CD3 + CD4 + YFP + Tregs (1×10^5) were pipetted into a 96-well U-bottom plate in 100 μ l final volume and stimulated overnight with IL-4 (10 ng/ml, Milteny Biotec) in R10 medium. Two control conditions are also analyzed: a) non-treated controls (NTC) with only T cell medium and b) pre-treatment with anti-IL-4 (1 μ g/ml, Biolegend, clone 11B11) for 30 minutes followed by IL-4 stimuli as described before. Next day, cells were harvested and analyzed via flow cytometry.

Statistics.

Statistics were calculated with Prism version 9.0 (GraphPad) using a two-tailed Mann–Whitney U comparison test or a two-way ANOVA test with Tukey's correction test, as specified in the figure legend. All data are presented as mean \pm SEM. P values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant, with $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$, $****p < 0.0001$. Graphs without stars are considered not significant.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Author contributions

A.B.W. and A.S. conceived the project and designed the experiments; A.H., S.K., C.K., C.D., A.G. and A.B.W. performed experiments; S.K. and A.G. performed the induction of allergic asthma disease and the AHR measurements; S.S. contributed to the paraffin embedding lung tissue; C.I.G. performed the H&E and Sirius red staining and critically evaluated the pathological features of the histological results. A.H. and A.B.W. analyzed the results and wrote the manuscript. S.F. advised regarding the interpretation of asthma data; S.F., S.K., C.I.G. and A.S. revised the manuscript; A.S. and A.B.W. supervised the project and acquired the funding.

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Figures

Figure 1

CD83cKO mice show a higher activation status and an impaired non-lymphoid-tissue (NLT) function. FACS analysis of Tregs from spleen (SPL) mesenteric lymph node- (mLN), and lungs of 8–12-week-old mice. **a** Frequencies of FoxP3⁺ Tregs among all living CD45⁺ in the respective organs **b-d** Surface receptor expression of ST2, KLRG1, and GITR on Tregs. (Ctrl n=4-10, CD83cKO n=4-10, pool of 3 independent experiments). In all graphs, data are represented as mean ± SEM and two-tailed Mann–Whitney U-test was used to analyze the data.

Figure 2

Lung resident lymphocytes of CD83cKO mice show escalating cytokine responses. Lung and cervical lymph node (cLN) derived lymphocytes were stimulated for 48 h with anti-CD3/anti-CD28. **a** Supernatant cytokine and **b** chemokine analysis of stimulated lung and cLN lymphocytes from 8–12-week-old mice. (Ctrl n=20-21, CD83cKO n= 20-21, pool of 6 independent experiments). In all graphs, data are represented as mean \pm SEM and two-tailed Mann–Whitney U-test was used to analyze the data.

Figure 3

CD83cKO mice showed increased AHR and pathological changes in lung morphology. **a** Graphical overview experimental procedure for the in vivo allergic asthma mouse model. **b** Non-invasive AHR measurement by whole-body plethysmography. Enhanced pause (Penh) has been calculated at baseline and after challenge with metacholine (Mch): 0 mg/ml: $p=0.4926$; 25 mg/ml: $p=0.1067$; 50 mg/ml: $p=0.0826$; **c** Invasive AHR analysis was performed and the resistance (Rrs) of the lung was calculated

upon methacholine challenge: 0 mg/ml: $p=0.938$; 12.5 mg/ml: $p=0.4068$. **d** Representative Sirius Red stainings of lung tissue from PBS or OVA-treated Ctrl and CD83cKO mice. Green arrows demonstrate enlarged bronchial epithelium and blue arrows indicate collagen deposition. **e** Thickness of the peribronchial collagen layer was quantified by dividing the collagen thickness beneath the bronchial epithelium by the bronchial diameter. Statistical analysis of AHR data was performed using a two-way ANOVA test with Tukey's correction test. Relative collagen thickness is represented as mean \pm SEM and two-tailed Mann-Whitney U-test was used to analyze the data. (Ctrl $n=4-5$, CD83cKO $n=4-5$, one representative experiment out of two).

Figure 4

CD83cKO mice developed an exacerbated eosinophilia in allergic asthma. FACS analysis of immune cells in the bronchoalveolar lavage-fluid (BALF) and lung tissue from asthmatic and control mice. a

Frequencies of CD45⁺ immune cells, **b** total CD11b⁺ cells as well as **c** eosinophils in the BALFs and lungs. **d** Frequencies of SiglecF^{high}-inflammatory eosinophils in lung tissue. (Ctrl n=4-5, CD83cKO n= 4-5, one representative experiment out of two). In all graphs, data are represented as mean \pm SEM and two-tailed Mann–Whitney U-test was used to analyze the data.

Figure 5

Asthmatic lungs derived from CD83cKO mice resulted in enhanced Th2 effector T cell responses and a highly activated phenotype. **a-f** FACS analysis of lung-resident CD4⁺ T cells and Tregs from asthmatic and control mice: **a** CD4⁺ T cell frequencies. Percentage of GITR⁺ cells among **b** CD4⁺ T cells and **c** on Tregs. **d** Th2 effector cells (Foxp3⁻GATA3⁺) frequencies in the CD4⁺ T cell population. **e** Representative FACS plots of ST2 and FoxP3 populations among CD4⁺ cells. **f** Analysis of ST2⁺ Foxp3⁻ effector cells, ST2⁺Foxp3⁺ Tregs and St2⁻Foxp3⁺ Tregs among lung-resident T cells, and median expression of FoxP3 on tissue-resident Tregs. **g** Cytokine and chemokine analysis of lung lymphocytes re-stimulated with OVA for 24 h. In all graphs, data are represented as mean ± SEM and two-tailed Mann–Whitney U-test was used to analyze the data. (Ctrl n=4-5, CD83cKO n= 4-5, one representative experiment out of two)

Figure 6

T cells from CD83cKO mice revealed a higher proliferation rate and a shewing towards Th2

differentiation. **a** Schematic overview of DC/T cell coculture: OVA/LPS-stimulated DCs are co-cultured with CellTrace™Violet (CTV)-labeled CD4⁺ T cells from wild-type or CD83cKO mice in the presence of stimuli (anti-CD3/anti-IFN γ /IL-4) for 4 days **b** Frequencies of Tregs (CD25⁺CD4⁺Foxp3⁺) among T cells, **c** GATA3⁺ T cells. **d** Replication index of T cells from co-cultures. **e** Median fluorescence of GITR and **f** CD25 on CD4⁺ T cells. **g** Assessment of IL-13 production in supernatants of co-cultures (Ctrl n=9,

CD83cKO n= 9, pool of 3 independent experiments). In all graphs, data are represented as mean \pm SEM and two-tailed Mann–Whitney U-test was used to analyze the data.

Figure 7

Sorted splenic Tregs derived from CD83cKO mice show an enhanced IL-4 responsiveness and an increased GITR expression. **a** Gene expression analysis of IL-4R α of sorted Tregs (CD3⁺CD4⁺YFP⁺) from

spleens of Ctrl and CD83cKO mice. **b-f** FACS analysis of sorted Tregs without any treatment (non-treated controls, NTC) or after stimulation with IL-4 for 24 h. **b** Median fluorescence of Foxp3, **c** CD25, **d** GITR, **e** ICOS and **f** CD69 were determined on Foxp3⁺ Tregs in relation to NTCs. (Ctrl n=6, CD83cKO n= 6-7, pool of 3 independent experiments). In all graphs, data are represented as mean ± SEM and two-tailed Mann-Whitney U-test was used to analyze the data.

Figure 8

Graphical summary

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